

HIGH PERFORMANCE COMPOSITE STRUCTURES FOR HIGH PRECISION PARTICLE DETECTORS

Claude Hauviller

PPE Division, CERN, 1211 GENEVA 23 - Switzerland

SUMMARY: After some background on High Energy Physics (HEP) and the future accelerator and its detectors, tracking detector principles are shortly described. Sources of errors which impinge the resolution of these so-called trackers are then analysed. It is shown that to achieve a measurement accuracy at the level of few microns over a huge detection volume of many cubic meters, it is of a prime importance that the support structures are as light as possible while providing a very high stability.

Optimisation leads to the choice of high performance composite structures. But an hostile environment leads to major concerns on the micron level stability of these structures: ionising radiations, temperature gradients, humidity transients, vibrations,... together with inherent mechanical behaviour: internal stresses, creep...

This general presentation will be enlighten with specific examples of composite structures for high precision particle detectors.

KEYWORDS: high energy particle physics, precision detector, lightweight structures, high performance composites, mechanical stability, environmental degradation

HIGH ENERGY PHYSICS AND ACCELERATORS

To satisfy the constant quest of the physics community to look deeper into matter, more powerful accelerators are always requested.

Now, with the LEP machine, the latest and largest of CERN's accelerators with a collision energy in the range of 200 GeV, we can probe the structure of matter down to the level of 10^{-18} meter. But new fundamental questions arose: yet undetected particle families leading to a better understanding of the dark matter in the Universe, why W and Z particles have such a high mass whereas a photon is massless,... and many ideas and scenarios for a better understanding of our so complex world. To get answers or at least clues, we need to achieve one order of magnitude in resolution down to 10^{-19} meter and that implies collision energies in the TeV range at the constituents level.

The LHC (Large Hadron Collider) is designed for that purpose [1]. This 27 km long proton-proton collider of 14 TeV centre-of-mass energy will recreate the conditions prevailing in the Universe just 10^{-12} second after the "Big Bang" when the temperature was 10^{16} degrees. But a high luminosity is also required to benefit from this increase of energy. The 10^{34} $\text{cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ design luminosity of LHC leads to events generated by the collisions with a huge number of particles to be analysed in some nanoseconds and an unusual high radiation level.

To analyse in fine details such complex interactions, detectors will have millions of measuring channels which should give accurate information on the mass, the charge, the momentum and the trajectory of each of the generated particles.

DETECTORS

A typical detector for LHC, shown in figure 1, will be installed around one of the interaction points. It has an overall cylindrical shape with both diameter and length up to 20 meters. The particle beams go through the detector along its axis and collide at the centre. Weighing up to 15,000 tons, a detector consists basically of three sub-systems embedded one inside the other like Russian dolls: an inner detector or tracker, the calorimeters and completely enclosing the others the muon system. In addition, a magnetic field deflecting particles to measure charge and momentum, is generated by one (or more) powerful electro-magnet.

Fig1.: LHC detector (scale is given by a person in front)

HIGH PRECISION DETECTORS: TRACKERS

General

If the precision is a major concern for all the elements of the detector, the more stringent specifications are found in the innermost part, the tracker.

A tracker, located in the immediate vicinity of the interaction point, is like any other detector a system which could be divided into a series of sub-systems : the detecting elements (the heart of the detector), the support structure, the electronics and data acquisition and the services: active gases, cooling (liquid and gas), power, alignment and survey.

Detecting Elements

As most of all the present detectors, the measuring techniques of the tracking detectors are based on the ionization and excitation phenomena produced by charged particles in gases and solids. The most common and oldest ones, the Wire Chambers measure the ionization produced by a charged particle in a gas; generated electrons produce a signal on precisely positioned wires. The accuracy currently achieved is only in the order of 100 microns. Moreover, the too high density of tracks at LHC leads to spatial separation difficulties and the rather slow time for signal development of about 100 ns, is incompatible with the LHC repetivity rate of 25 ns (time between two subsequent particle bunches collisions).

Momentum measurements and particle identification require now a precision in the reconstruction of the particle trajectories in some cases better than the ten microns level. The more precise devices are the silicon or gallium arsenide or diamond strip detecting elements. The first ones are the most common ones. They are made of high resistivity doped silicon wafers, 300 microns thick. The two other types are based on the same principle with a different substrate, with the advantage of a better radiation resistance.

Narrow strips are ion implanted with a pitch of usually 50 microns. The signal is measured at the strip end in less than 20 ns and the measurement precision is around 10 microns and even could go down to 3 microns with the most sophisticated electronics devices. It is even possible to measure two co-ordinates with a double-sided detector or with an other type of device, the pixel detector where the electrodes are in the form of pads.

In the detectors presently taking data, this strip technology is only applied in rather small volumes, some decimetre cube.

Other types of detecting elements are used when the required accuracy is only around 50 microns: the Microstrip Gas Chambers (MSGC), the Straw tubes and the Scintillating fibres.

The Support Structure

Except very seldom cases, the detecting strips/wires are laid either parallel or perpendicular to the particle beams axis to simplify (or even permit) the tracks reconstruction. Therefore, the support structures have quite simple overall shape : planar or cylindrical. They are manufactured from shells, plates and cross-braced lattices. But, as it will be shown later, space and mass constraints complicate drastically the design.

DETECTOR RESOLUTION

If it has been possible to work at a resolution better than 10 microns in small detecting volumes, now the aim for the near future is to achieve almost the same precision inside huge volumes of tens of cubic meters. This step in the technology is obviously a major challenge.

To fully use the very high intrinsic resolution of the detecting elements, it is of the utmost importance not to spoil it in the fully assembled detector. Main sources of errors on the measurement of a particle trajectory are mainly due to the intrinsic resolution of the detecting element and the performance of its electronics, the multiple scattering created by all the materials of the detector and the mechanical positioning and stability in the 3-dimensional space. The total error is the r. m. s. of these errors.

Multiple Scattering

Electrically charged particles suffer multiple scattering caused by electromagnetic interactions with electrons and nuclei when traversing a medium. Loss of energy is small but large scattering angles are major sources of errors in the momentum definition.

The r. m. s. scattering angle θ_p is given by

$$\theta_p = \frac{0.014}{\beta p} \sqrt{\frac{L}{X_0}} \quad (1)$$

where

$\beta = v/c$

p in GeV/c

L length of material traversed by the particle

X_0 radiation length is a physical property of the material

Its approximate value, expressed in meters, is

$$X_0 = 7.16 \frac{A}{\rho Z(Z+1) \ln(287/\sqrt{Z})} \quad (2)$$

where

ρ is the density

A is the atomic mass

Z is the atomic number

In first approximation, X_0 is roughly inversely proportional to ρZ .

Positioning Stability

The mechanical design of the support structures is based on deflection and, usually, not on stress. Many sources of vibrations (inherent to the earth itself or to the infrastructure : pumps, motors, ventilation,...) exist in an experimental hall and will undoubtedly generate displacements in the microns range. Therefore, it is necessary to maximise the rigidity which could be expressed in general terms as the product of the Young's modulus (E) (the material should behave in its elastic range) by a length (L). Taking into account the necessary minimisation of the multiple scattering, the previous product can be written as $E X_0$, an expression depending only upon the material. As a consequence, this product $E X_0$ can be used as figure of merit for all the structural materials of the detectors and both the Young's

modulus and the radiation length should be as high as possible. Figure 2 shows a comparison of some of the best representatives of material families available on the market (unidirectional properties).

All these materials are also known for their high specific stiffness (E/ρ) and it is therefore obvious that the selection criterion $E X_0$ will lead to a choice very similar to the one for aeronautics and space [2],[3].

Fig. 2: Figures of merit for structural materials for trackers.

LIFE CYCLE OF A TRACKER

Operational Life

Design and construction of the present detectors will extend over more than ten years. The detectors will be assembled and fully tested in temperature and humidity controlled clean rooms. But the environmental conditions during the transport to and installation inside the underground hall will be more or less the atmospheric conditions.

The detectors are designed for ten years of operation in the radiative environment of the LHC. Each year of operation will be basically split into two equal periods: the data-taking period and the maintenance period. The tracker should stay very precise during the data-taking period, at least between two tricky on-line calibrations. During the maintenance period, the irradiation is stopped but temperature and humidity excursions may be large.

Environmental Conditions

A stiff structure will not necessary be stable, especially if the environmental conditions are too harsh. One should take into account the radiation, the temperature, the humidity and the vibrations . Table 1 summarises these parameters.

The very high luminosity of the LHC generated by a high radiative environment inside the detectors is largely above the radiation level in the present accelerators. The expected fluences inside the tracker volume are, for an integrated luminosity of 10^{42}cm^{-2} (ten years of LHC running at nominal conditions), for the charged particles, $\phi = 1.3 \cdot 10^{17}/r^2 \text{ cm}^{-2}$, where r is the distance from the particle beam axis in centimetres and for the neutrons, $\phi = 3 \cdot 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, constant inside the tracker volume.

The resulting integrated dose goes therefore up to the Megagray range.

Dynamic measurements on present detectors have shown movements in the range of some microns. These movements have two origins [4]: the ground motion (seismic) in the low frequency range (below 1Hz), the man-made vibrations/noise created by ventilation, fluids in tubes, pumps (in particular cryogenics),...

Table 1: Typical environmental conditions (detecting element dependant)

	Data-Taking	Assembly/Maintenance
Radiation	Yearly integrated dose up to 100 KGray	None
Temperature	Nominal temperature between -15 °C and 30 °C Stability +/- 1 °C Local hot spots (electronics)	Nominal temperature between 5 °C and 25 °C
Humidity	Dry gas : N2, CO2 Some % relative humidity	Atmospheric, between 20% and 80% relative humidity
Vibrations	Ground (seismic) motion Man-made noise	Ditto

MATERIALS SELECTION

Optimal Material

In résumé, an optimal structural material for a tracker should fulfil the following criteria:
 light (high X_0),
 stiff (high E),
 radiation resistant (radiation index > 6),
 insensitive to temperature variations (low CTE),
 insensitive to humidity variations (low CME and moisture absorption),
 stable with time.

It is not very surprising to find that no material can fulfil all these requirements selection. A relative priority should be set between the different criteria. But this material choice should also be directed largely by other major factors:

the way to tackle the safety problems,
the availability of the material in rather small quantities,
the technological limitations,
and last but not least of the final cost of the manufactured parts.

Selection

The first two criteria (X_0 and E) are used as bases for the choice. Figure 2 shows that some metals, metal based composites and ceramics stand very high in the comparison, but they are hampered by serious drawbacks, mainly technological limitations and cost.

Manufacturing large structures in beryllium has been demonstrated in the space program. But it is not only costly, safety hazards are not negligible. Moreover, the technology to connect elements is difficult, leading to too bulky elements, even if welding is now becoming possible.

All these arguments are also true for beryllium - aluminium alloys. The only parts which have been manufactured yet with the others competitors (diamond, carbon-carbon, boron-carbide, metal matrix composites, silicon-carbide) are too small to be considered in the short term despite a good resistance to radiation and a relative insensitivity to humidity.

Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastics

The material chosen is therefore the Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastics (CFRP) family with high and ultra-high modulus fibres. The detailed choice of the components of the material for each structure depends upon its specifications. Pan fibres are the classical ones but pitch fibres are preferred when compressive stresses are small and when high thermal conductivity is a must to avoid local hot spots.

Environmental conditions specified earlier may create serious difficulties which are examined thereafter.

The plastics should be high performance plastics in order to resist radiation. An extensive source of information prepared at CERN like [5] are used as guidelines. It has been found that, for most of the plastics, one finds a correlation between the curing temperature and the radiation resistance. The two selected families of resins in terms of radiation and also in terms of manufacturing possibilities are the epoxies and the cyanate-esters.

In terms of behaviour versus temperature, CFRP is very good. The thermal properties are well known; it is possible to use lay-ups giving an almost zero coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) and the transients in time are very short.

But in terms of the behaviour versus humidity, one finds major drawbacks: all the resins absorb humidity (up to 6% for epoxies) and the transients are in the range of months, which could lead to a large shortening of the data-taking period due to the instability of the structures. Limited work has been done in this field, but one can see in figure 3 that humidity

transients may lead to large strain variations: it takes more than two months to start to stabilise for a 0.5mm thick sample after a jump in relative humidity of only 20% [6].

Fig.3: Hygroscopic strains (*Hercules 3501-5/T300 uniaxial composite*)

Above that, one should also take into account the macroscopic phenomena changing materials properties with time: creep occurs even at a low load level, internal stresses built-in during the manufacturing process relax more or less quickly (one should note that a lower curing temperature will limit the level of the internal stresses, but this requirement will be in conflict with a higher curing temperature for a better radiation resistance), micro-cracks propagate slowly, and the coupling effects of radiation is basically unknown.

Moreover, in the case of materials in contact with the highly pure detecting gas of a detector, resins with low outgassing should be chosen in order to avoid any pollution.

EXAMPLES OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES FOR TRACKERS

If High Modulus Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastics has been chosen as base material for the high precision detectors of the future, one sees that a large series of phenomena are not really entirely understood. The present design is based on the present knowledge, but specific development are going on to try to understand better how the specific environment will worsen the performances of the detectors and to try to avoid bad surprises. A large series of diverse composites structures are under design and prototyping with a construction to be completed by the end of the century. Two examples are presented below.

The ATLAS TRT Barrel Structure

This full CFRP structure (Figure 4) holds precisely positioned axial detecting elements assembled in a cylindrical overall shape (2 m in diameter, 1.6 m in length). The end faces are cross braced structures designed to minimise the material quantity and to give as much space as possible to the data acquisition equipment and the services. The two end faces are connected together by two thin cylinders. The only support points are two rails.

Fig.4: The ATLAS TRT barrel structure

If the trusses (5x20mm) are made of uniaxial fibres, major difficulties lay in the treatment of the connections: how to transfer the forces without increasing the dimensions of the nodes. First prototypes made by simply gluing the trusses together show unexpectedly large deflections, very different from the ones obtained by FEM analysis. More complex solutions like continuous winding could be an alternate, but costly solution.

The CMS MSGC Barrel Structure

Fig. 5: A CMS MSGC barrel end-plate

This large structure is also cylindrical, but with larger dimensions: 2350 mm in diameter and 2300 mm in length. The two carbon-fibre end-plates (figure 5) support rigid composites slabs

housing the detecting elements and their services. The slots supporting the slabs should be precisely machined in a sandwich plate. The end-plates are connected together by two cylinders and two extra thinner plates reinforce the structure and minimise the sag of the slabs.

CONCLUSION

A tracker is an assembly of a series of sub-systems and its performances will be dependant of the worse of these sub-systems. The detecting elements have an outstanding behaviour and the support structures should behave accordingly. An approach of cost-effective design has led to high performance dimensionally stable structures for space applications manufactured in Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastics. Even if the operational life, in particular the environmental conditions, of the future HEP trackers will be different, the principles and methods developed for space are applicable to the manufacturing of these structures. CFRP is presently the only technologically sound material for these applications but major concerns still exist, in the lack of knowledge of its behaviour versus parameters like humidity and moreover about possible coupling between environmental parameters leading to unexpected properties degradation. In these conditions, it is a major challenge to build reliable structures at the uppermost limit of the technology.

Finally, the HEP community has definitively one common interest with the Space community, the High Performance Composites Structures and in the near future the loop will be closed when sophisticated particle trackers will be sent into space to study matter far from all the perturbations of our Earth [7].

REFERENCES

1. LHC, the Large Hadron Collider Accelerator Project, *CERN/AC/93-03*, November 1993, see also <http://www.cern.ch/>
2. Nicquevert, B. and Hauviller, C., Eds., International Workshop on Advanced Materials for High Precision Detectors, *CERN 94-07*, September 1994.
3. International Workshop on Advanced Materials for Lightweight Structures '94, 22-25 March, 1994, ESA-ESTEC, Noordwijk, The Netherlands
4. Juravlev, V.M., et al., Seismic Vibration Studies for Future Linear Colliders, Fourth European Particle Accelerator Conference (EPAC 94) London, UK, June 1994.
5. Schönbacher, H. and Tavlet, M., Compilation of radiation test data, *CERN 89-12*, Geneva, 1989.
6. Kanoute, P., et al., Diffuse and hygroelastic behavior of reinforced composites materials, European Conference on Surfaces and Interfaces in Polymers and Composites, Lausanne, Switzerland, June 1997
7. Battiston, R., Astro-Particle Physics with Alpha Magnetic Spectrometer (AMS), Workshop on Frontier Objects in Astrophysics and Particle Physics, Vulcano, Italy, May 1996